

MEDICAL SCIENCES

VITAMIN D STATUS IN PREGNANT WOMEN AND ITS IMPACT ON NEWBORNS

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Vitamin D plays a key role in calcium–phosphorus metabolism, immune regulation, and normal fetal development. Vitamin D deficiency during pregnancy is common and has been associated with an increased risk of adverse obstetric and neonatal outcomes, including preterm birth (PTB) and low birth weight (LBW).

Aim: To evaluate vitamin D status in pregnant women and to investigate its association with the risk of preterm birth and low birth weight.

Materials and Methods: A prospective study was conducted between 2019 and 2021 in Varna, Bulgaria, including 259 pregnant women. Participants were divided into three groups: healthy pregnant women, women with gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM), and women with preeclampsia (PE). Demographic and clinical data, information on vitamin D intake, and serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D [25(OH)D] concentrations were collected. Serum 25(OH)D levels were measured using a validated LC–MS method. Associations between vitamin D status, gestational age at delivery, and neonatal birth weight were analyzed.

Results: Preterm birth occurred in 12.45% of newborns, with the highest incidence observed among women with PE. Low birth weight was recorded in 13.23% of newborns, again most frequently in the PE group. A statistically significant association was found between maternal vitamin D intake and neonatal birth weight ($p < 0.0001$). In women with PE and in healthy pregnant women, higher vitamin D intake and higher serum 25(OH)D levels were associated with a lower risk of PTB and LBW. Correlation analysis demonstrated a positive association between serum 25(OH)D concentrations and gestational age, particularly in women with PE.

Conclusion: The findings of this study support the hypothesis that inadequate vitamin D status during pregnancy is associated with an increased risk of preterm birth and low birth weight, especially among women with preeclampsia. Optimization of vitamin D status through adequate supplementation may represent a safe, accessible, and cost-effective strategy for improving perinatal outcomes. Further large-scale randomized controlled trials are required to confirm these findings and to establish clear clinical recommendations.

Keywords: vitamin D, 25(OH)D, pregnancy, outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

Vitamin D plays a crucial role in calcium-phosphorus metabolism, skeletal development, and immune regulation. During pregnancy, adequate maternal vitamin D levels are essential not only for the health of the mother but also for the proper growth and development of the fetus [1]. Numerous studies have identified a consistent and strong association between maternal vitamin D deficiency and adverse pregnancy and birth outcomes, including an increased risk of preeclampsia (PE), gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM), preterm birth (PTB), low birth weight (LBW), and postpartum complications [2, 3].

Despite the well-established importance of vitamin D during pregnancy, hypovitaminosis D remains highly prevalent worldwide – particularly in regions with limited sunlight exposure, inadequate dietary intake, or cultural practices that reduce skin exposure [4]. Newborns rely entirely on maternal stores and placental transfer of vitamin D, making maternal status a critical determinant of neonatal vitamin D sufficiency [5].

Given the crucial role of vitamin D in maternal and fetal health, recent research has increasingly focused on its potential impact on specific pregnancy outcomes – particularly PTB and LBW.

PTB continues to be the leading cause of neonatal mortality globally and the second most common cause of death in children under five years of age [6]. The etiology of PTB is multifactorial and complex, involving genetic, environmental, immunological, and nutritional factors. Among these, vitamin D deficiency during pregnancy has gained increasing attention due to its potential role in modulating immune responses and inflammation – mechanisms thought to contribute to the onset of preterm labor [7].

LBW remains a significant global public health concern due to its association with increased neonatal morbidity and long-term adverse health outcomes [8]. Multiple studies have explored the potential role of maternal vitamin D deficiency in the etiology of LBW, given vitamin D's essential functions in fetal growth and development [9].

AIM

The aim of this study is to evaluate the vitamin D status in pregnant women and investigate its potential association with neonatal outcomes, specifically the risk of PTB and LBW. By analyzing maternal serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D (25(OH)D) concentrations and supplementation during pregnancy and correlating

them with pregnancy outcomes, the study seeks to determine whether maternal vitamin D sufficiency can serve as a protective factor against these adverse events.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The research is prospective in character and has taken place in the Diagnostic and Consulting Centre of “St Marina” University Hospital, Acibadem City Clinic Medical Center, Specialized Hospital for Obstetrics and Gynecology for Active Treatment “Prof. Dr D. Stamatov”, and General Hospital for Active Treatment “St. Anna” in Varna, from 02.07.2019 to 31.12.2021. A total of 259 pregnant women had been included in the scientific research. They filled in a questionnaire card that contained demographic data and information connected to their life style, the course of previous pregnancies (if there were such) and their obstetric outcomes, as well as a family history.

All pregnant women included in the clinical trial after getting acquainted and signing the informed consent form are asked to fill in a survey card, under doctor’s supervision who is a participant in the survey. It contains demographic data and information related to their style of life (diet, physical activity, administration of medicines and dietary supplements), data about previous pregnancies and obstetric results, family history.

The quantitative analyses of the circulating form of vitamin D in blood serum were tested in the Department of Biochemistry, Molecular Medicine and Nutrigenomics at the Faculty of Pharmacy, Medical University, Varna. To achieve this goal validated LC-MS method with UV detection for identification and quantitative analysis of 25(OH)D in blood serum was used.

RESULTS

A total of 259 pregnant women were enrolled in the study. Of these, 210 women (81.08%) were evaluated as outpatients, while 49 women (18.91%) were hospitalized and treated as inpatients for PE at the Specialized Hospital for Obstetrics and Gynecology for Active Treatment ‘Prof. Dr. D. Stamatov’, Varna. The

average age of participants was 30.5 years (range 19 – 49 years).

The majority of participants were of Bulgarian origin (89.57%, n=232), resided in a large city (90.35%, n=234), were married (55.21%, n=143), and had attained higher education (56.37%, n=146). Most participants (94.20%, n=244) did not have concomitant chronic or non-systemic diseases. Based on their health status, participants were classified into three major groups:

Group I: Healthy pregnant women (n=167, 64.5%). Among them, 114 (68.3%) were in the second trimester and 53 (31.7%) in the third trimester.

Group II: Pregnant women with GDM (n=43, 16.6%). Of these, 26 (60.5%) were in the second trimester and 17 (39.5%) in the third trimester. GDM diagnosis was based on an OGTT with 75 g of glucose administered between the 24th and 28th GW, or at another time during pregnancy, following the IDF (2013) and WHO (2013) criteria.

Group III: Pregnant women with PE (n=49, 18.9%). Of these, 6 (12.2%) were in the second trimester and 43 (87.8%) in the third trimester. All diagnoses were based on established clinical criteria, and participants were hospitalized in the Department of Pregnancy Pathology at the same hospital.

Vitamin D Status and Risk of PTB

In the present study, 32 out of 257 newborns (12.45%) were delivered preterm, indicating a notable rate of PTB. The highest incidence was observed among pregnant women with PE, where 45.83% (n = 22) of cases resulted in PTB. In comparison, the prevalence was 6.98% (n = 3) among those with GDM and 4.21% (n = 7) in the healthy control group.

To evaluate the potential role of maternal vitamin D status in the occurrence of PTB, we initially analyzed the frequency of this complication in relation to vitamin D intake. Participants were categorized based on their reported intake of vitamin D from pharmaceutical preparations and/or dietary supplements as follows: no intake, intake below 600 IU/day, and intake above 600 IU/day (Table 1).

Table 1

Distribution of Pregnant Women by Gestational Age and Vitamin D Supplementation (Entire Cohort)

Gestational Age	No Intake N (%)	<600 IU/day N (%)	>600 IU/day N (%)	Total N (%)
>37 weeks	73 (32.4%)	101 (44.9%)	51 (22.7%)	225 (100%)
<37 weeks	12 (37.5%)	15 (46.9%)	5 (15.6%)	32 (100%)

The results presented in Table 1 indicate that a similar proportion of women who delivered at term and those who experienced PTB were supplemented with vitamin D at doses below the recommended minimum of 600 IU/day (44.89% vs. 46.88%, respectively). The proportion of women who did not receive any vitamin D supplementation was higher among those who delivered preterm compared to those who delivered at term (37.50% vs. 32.44%, respectively). Conversely, a greater proportion of women who delivered at term received adequate vitamin D supplementation (>600 IU/day) compared to those with PTB (22.67% vs. 15.62%, respectively). A non-parametric chi-square

analysis was conducted to evaluate potential differences between the groups; however, no statistically significant association was found ($\chi^2 = 0.879$, $p = 0.645$).

We also investigated the vitamin D intake among women from the three main groups who experienced PTB. Based on the frequency distribution, we can conclude that among healthy pregnant women and those with PE, the likelihood of PTB is lower in those who received adequate vitamin D supplementation (>600 IU/day) compared to those who were either not supplemented or supplemented with a lower dose (<600 IU/day). This trend, however, was not observed in the group of women with GDM.

Using Spearman correlation analysis, we investigated the association of PTB in the three main study groups with both vitamin D intake and serum concentrations of 25(OH)D. The results of the analysis are presented in Table 2. A positive and moderately strong correlation was found between serum levels of 25(OH)D and gestational age in women with PE ($\rho=0.358, p=0.016$), as well as between serum levels of 25(OH)D and vitamin D supplementation ($\rho=0.410, p=0.014$). This indicates that the likelihood of PTB decreases with increasing vitamin D intake and serum levels of 25(OH)D. Among healthy pregnant

women, an increasing risk of PTB was observed with decreasing vitamin D intake during pregnancy ($\rho=0.273, p=0.007$), and a moderate correlation was found between vitamin D supplementation and serum 25(OH)D levels ($\rho=0.498, p<0.0001$). In the group of women with GDM, a strong correlation was found between vitamin D supplementation and serum 25(OH)D levels ($\rho=0.848, p<0.0001$), but the weakly increasing risk of PTB with decreasing vitamin D intake and serum levels of 25(OH)D did not reach statistical significance ($\rho=0.167, p=0.416$ and $\rho=0.138, p=0.382$, respectively).

Table 2

Spearman’s Correlation Between Vitamin D Intake, Serum 25(OH)D and Pregnancy Duration by Group

Group	Variable	Normal Gestation/PTB	Vitamin D Intake	Serum 25(OH)D nmol/l
Healthy Pregnant Women	Normal Gestation/PTB	1.000	0.273**	0.052
	Vitamin D Intake	0.273**	1.000	0.498**
	Serum 25(OH)D (nmol/l)	0.052	0.498**	1.000
	p-value	.	0.007	0.524
Women with GDM	Normal Gestation/PTB	1.000	0.167	0.138
	Vitamin D Intake	0.167	1.000	0.848**
	Serum 25(OH)D (nmol/l)	0.138	0.848**	1.000
	p-value	.	0.416	0.382
Women with PE	Normal Gestation/PTB	1.000	0.314	0.358*
	Vitamin D Intake	0.314	1.000	0.410*
	Serum 25(OH)D (nmol/l)	0.358*	0.410*	1.000
	p-value	.	0.055	0.016

Vitamin D Status and Risk of LBW

We used a similar approach to assess the influence of vitamin D status in pregnant women on LBW. Table 3 shows the frequency distribution of pregnant women

based on vitamin D supplementation and the birth weight of their newborns for the entire studied cohort.

Table 3

Frequency Distribution of Pregnant Women Based on Vitamin D Supplementation and the Birth Weight of Their Newborns for the Entire Studied Cohort

Birth Weight	No Vitamin D Supplementation N (%)	Vitamin D Supplementation <600 IU/day N (%)	Vitamin D Supplementation >600 IU/day N (%)	Total N (%)
Normal Weight (>2500g)	58 (26.00%)	113 (50.67%)	52 (23.32%)	223 (100%)
Low Weight (<2500g)	27 (79.41%)	5 (14.70%)	2 (5.88%)	34 (100%)

Results presented in Table 3 show that the percentage of non-supplemented women who delivered a LBW infant is three times higher than that of women who delivered a newborn with normal weight (79.41% vs. 26.00%, respectively). Among those supplemented with vitamin D at doses <600 IU/day, the ratio is reversed – there is a 3.45-fold decrease in the percentage of LBW deliveries (50.67% vs. 14.70%). In women

who received adequate supplementation (>600 IU/day), the percentage drops nearly fourfold (23.32% vs. 5.88%). A chi-square test confirmed that the distribution shown in Table 3 is statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 38.02, p < 0.0001$).

We also analyzed the vitamin D intake among women from the three main groups who gave birth to LBW infants. Based on their frequency distribution, we

can conclude that among healthy pregnant women and those with PE, the likelihood of delivering a LBW infant is lower in those who were supplemented with an adequate dose of vitamin D (>600 IU/day) compared to those who were either not supplemented or supplemented with a low dose of vitamin D (<600 IU/day).

This trend was not observed in the group of women with GDM.

We also compared the mean values for vitamin D intake and serum 25(OH)D levels between pregnant women who delivered normal-weight infants and those who delivered LBW infants using an independent samples t-test (Table 4).

Table 4

Comparison of mean values of vitamin D intake and serum 25(OH)D concentrations in women who delivered normal weight vs. LBW newborns (entire cohort)

	Birth Weight	Mean \pm SD	95% CI	t-test (p)
Vitamin D intake (IU/day)	Normal	824.26 \pm 2167.65	[-58.7; 11.98]	$t = 0.667, p = 0.506$
	LBW	525.00 \pm 810.39		
25(OH)D (nmol/L)	Normal	76.17 \pm 38.33	[-13.22; 14.94]	$t = 0.121, p = 0.904$
	LBW	75.31 \pm 40.40		

It is notable that the mean vitamin D intake was lower (525 \pm 810.39 IU/day) among women who delivered a LBW infant compared to those who gave birth to a newborn with normal weight (824.26 \pm 2167 IU/day), and it falls below the recommended minimum intake of 600 IU/day. Nevertheless, the comparative analysis did not reveal a statistically significant difference in the mean intake values between the two groups ($t = 0.667, p = 0.506$), likely due to the large standard deviation. No statistically significant difference was found in the serum 25(OH)D levels between the two groups either (76.17 \pm 38.33 vs. 75.31 \pm 40.40, $t = 0.121, p = 0.904$).

DISCUSSION

1. PTB

A growing body of literature has explored the association between maternal vitamin D status and the risk of PTB; however, findings remain inconsistent. Agarwal et al. (2018) proposed that insufficient vitamin D levels during gestation may suppress immune function and alter the pathophysiological pathways leading to PTB [10]. Nevertheless, a meta-analysis conducted by Lian et al. (2021) did not find a statistically significant correlation between vitamin D deficiency in any trimester and the risk of PTB. Specifically, 13 out of the 24 observational studies included in the analysis reported no association between low maternal 25(OH)D concentrations and PTB [11].

Contradictory evidence also exists. Several studies have demonstrated a clear link between low maternal vitamin D levels and an increased risk of PTB [12, 13]. Moreover, sufficient maternal vitamin D status – commonly defined as serum 25(OH)D levels above 100 nmol/L – has been associated with a 60% reduction in the risk of PTB [10].

In our study, the incidence of PTB was 12.45%, with 32 of 257 newborns delivered before term. Notably, two-thirds of these cases occurred in women diagnosed with PE, a known risk factor for PTB. Within the PE group, we observed the strongest association between vitamin D status and PTB. This group also demonstrated the lowest levels of vitamin D supplementation (with 57.14% reporting no intake) and the lowest serum 25(OH)D concentrations (median: 53.80 nmol/L, IQR: 42.23–67.05 nmol/L). These findings underscore the potential relevance of maternal vitamin D

status in the pathogenesis of PTB, particularly among women with pre-existing pregnancy complications such as PE.

Additional studies support these observations. Bodnar et al. (2014) reported that nearly half of women who delivered preterm had 25(OH)D levels below 75 nmol/L [9]. Similarly, Agarwal et al. (2018) and McDonnell et al. (2017) observed a markedly reduced risk of PTB in mothers with sufficient vitamin D levels (>100 nmol/L) [10, 14]. Despite these promising findings, not all studies are in agreement. For instance, Baker et al. (2011) found no statistically significant difference in vitamin D levels between women who delivered at term and those who experienced PTB between 23 and 35 weeks of gestation [15].

These discrepancies may be attributed to differences in study design, population characteristics, definitions of vitamin D sufficiency, and methods of 25(OH)D measurement. The heterogeneity of these factors complicates direct comparison and underscores the necessity for well-designed randomized controlled trials (RCTs) to confirm causality and inform clinical guidelines.

2. LBW

Several biological mechanisms have been proposed to explain how maternal vitamin D status may influence neonatal birth weight. One hypothesis suggests that low maternal serum 25(OH)D concentrations impair fetal skeletal growth and mineralization, leading to reduced birth weight. Another postulated mechanism involves vitamin D's anti-inflammatory properties and its role in modulating placental function. In this context, vitamin D deficiency may contribute to placental inflammation, thereby increasing the risk of intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) and LBW [16, 17].

Additionally, vitamin D has been linked to the regulation of insulin-like growth factor 1 (IGF-1), a hormone involved in fetal growth signaling. Evidence from adult populations suggests that vitamin D supplementation increases IGF-1 levels, implying that maternal deficiency could lead to impaired fetal growth through this pathway [16]. Despite these plausible mechanisms, the existing literature presents conflicting findings. While some studies have demonstrated a positive correlation between maternal 25(OH)D levels and

neonatal birth weight [18], others have reported no significant association [19].

Our study found an overall incidence of LBW of 13.23% (n = 34), with the highest prevalence observed in women with PE – 33.33% (n = 16). In comparison, LBW rates among participants with gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) and healthy pregnancies were 13.95% (n = 6) and 7.23% (n = 12), respectively. A significant association was identified between maternal vitamin D intake and neonatal birth weight ($\chi^2 = 38.02$, $p < 0.0001$), particularly among women with PE and healthy participants.

Although the difference in mean daily vitamin D intake between mothers of normal-weight (824.26 ± 2167.65 IU/day) and LBW infants (525.00 ± 810.39 IU/day) did not reach statistical significance – likely due to the wide variability in supplement dosages – it may still indicate a clinically meaningful trend. Similarly, no statistically significant difference was found in serum 25(OH)D concentrations between the two groups (76.17 ± 38.33 nmol/L vs. 75.31 ± 40.40 nmol/L; $p = 0.904$). This lack of significance could be due to confounding factors such as seasonality, sun exposure, diet, and physical activity, which were not controlled for in the current analysis. The relatively small number of LBW cases also limited our ability to perform stratified analyses and identify the most influential variables.

The inconsistent findings in our study mirror the broader literature, where randomized controlled trials have yielded mixed results. Nevertheless, the majority of systematic reviews and meta-analyses – such as the one conducted by Maugeri et al. (2019) – suggest a positive effect of maternal vitamin D supplementation on neonatal birth weight [20]. These findings support the hypothesis that optimizing vitamin D status during pregnancy may be a simple and cost-effective strategy for improving fetal growth and reducing the risk of LBW.

CONCLUSION

The present study supports the hypothesis that vitamin D deficiency during pregnancy may be associated with an increased risk of adverse outcomes such as PTB and LBW. Although a statistically significant causal relationship was not consistently demonstrated, the observed correlations between vitamin D intake, serum 25(OH)D levels, and the occurrence of these complications highlight the potential role of this micronutrient in maintaining a healthy pregnancy.

Historically, vitamin D supplementation has led to one of the most significant achievements in public health – the global elimination of rickets. In the modern context, attention has shifted toward the exploration of vitamin D's non-calcemic effects, including its impact on immune regulation, inflammation, and placental function. This is particularly relevant in vulnerable populations such as pregnant women and newborns.

Lifestyle modifications, combined with timely identification and correction of vitamin D deficiency, could represent an effective, accessible, and low-risk strategy for improving perinatal outcomes and promoting long-term maternal and child health. However, further randomized controlled trials with larger cohorts are

needed to confirm the observed trends and to develop clear clinical recommendations.

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